

Additional information about the participants of the second survey

#	Role (anonymized)	Industry	No. of employees (worldwide)
1	Chief executive officer	Marketing agency	10 – 49
2	Head of sales	IT service provider	
3	Managing partner	Management consulting	
4	Chief operating officer	Manufacturing	50 – 249
5	Chief technology officer	Manufacturing	
6	Head of human resources and finance	Manufacturing	
7	Chief executive officer	Manufacturing	250 – 499
8	Head of sales	Marketing agency	1,000 – 2,499
9	Site manager	Manufacturing	
10	Head of IT	Utilities	
11	Head of automation	Manufacturing	
12	Department head	Hospital	5,000 – 9,999
13	Leading physician	Hospital	
14	Business process manager	Manufacturing	≥ 10,000
15	Segment manager	Banking	
16	Product manager	Manufacturing	
17	Head of customer satisfaction	Software development	<i>Not available</i>
18	Member of supervisory board	Real estate	<i>Not available</i>